

Survey and Classification of Antennas for Medical Applications

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Abstract— This manuscript provides a comprehensive survey of various antenna types used in microwave medical applications. This research is the first step towards the development of a thorough numerical library containing various components used in microwave medical systems such as antennas, phantoms, matching media, etc. The goal of this effort is to enable researchers in this field to efficiently and easily test their algorithms and/or hardware using standardized components. In addition, such a library would encourage considering the whole system instead of partial approach in which, for e.g., developing imaging algorithms ignored the physical sensors etc. Here, we consider various antenna designs that have emerged in the last two decades. In particular, we discuss the chronological evolution of antennas for hyperthermia, biotelemetry and microwave imaging. We also classify antennas with respect to utilized frequency band, such as Medical Implant Communication Service (MICS), Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) Radio Bands, and Ultra Wide-Band (UWB).

Index Terms— Antenna, Hyperthermia, Microwave Imaging, Telemetry.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been an emerging interest in medical application of microwave imaging systems (MIS). Conventional technologies such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT), although still considered as gold standards in medical diagnostics, have several limitations. MRI systems are extremely costly, non-transportable and have long examination time. This is particularly restrictive in e.g., brain imaging where fragile patient conditions require portable bedside instruments. Further, CT and mammography imaging modalities use ionizing radiation, which is hazardous and increases the risk of cancer incidence [1].

An increased interest in microwave medical imaging systems resulted in development of its individual components, one of which is antenna. Due to the numerical complexity of the electromagnetic (EM) modeling and required computational power, the performance of the antennas is typically evaluated separately from the whole MIS. Even within the same class of applications, the antennas differ significantly with respect to their type, size, directivity, bandwidth, mutual coupling, etc. In addition, besides large variety in antenna design, there has been no consensus about the optimal number of sensors (antennas) to be used in MIS. For e.g., in brain imaging, the number of

array elements vary from 24 [2] to 117 [3]. Similarly, due to the same computational cost, the imaging algorithms have often been tested using simplified sensors and/or simplified phantoms. However, to assess accurately the performance of an inverse algorithm, it is necessary to utilize phantoms that are fundamentally alike to real life tissues and human bodies. In addition, standardized phantoms are necessary to compare different methods.

Hence, researchers working in medical MIS would significantly benefit from a software platform containing libraries of various antennas, tissues, phantoms, and matching media. The existence of such facility would enable realistic performance evaluation of different aspects of microwave imaging efforts as well as fair comparison between results obtained by different groups.

The development of such a platform represents a part of the ongoing project Electromagnetic Imaging for a Novel Generation of Medical Devices (EMERALD) [4]. As a first step within this task, we plan to develop a library comprising EM models of major antenna designs. For this purpose, we put a substantial effort to make a detailed survey of antennas used in microwave medical applications. Besides microwave imaging, we included applications such as hyperthermia and biotelemetry. Therefore, the goal of this paper is to present an initial survey of various antennas used in microwave imaging and associated medical application. In particular, the antennas are classified with structural survey based on application and frequency bandwidth.

II. CLASSIFICATION OF ANTENNAS

A. Antennas for Biomedical Application

Fig. 2.1 illustrates selected medical applications and their stratification in the clinical field. Various antenna designs were studied and developed to achieve optimum performance.

a) Thermal Application (Hyperthermia)

We start our survey with hyperthermia or thermotherapy, which is a cancer treatment that involves heating tumor cells to temperatures 40 – 44 °C [5]. The temperature of the tissue is raised due to the absorption of radio frequency (RF) or microwave power described by a specific absorption rate (SAR). Antenna models for hyperthermia applications are

reported in [6], [7-12]. A very basic helical antenna is proposed in [5] by removing a part of outer conductor from one end of the coaxial cable and the copper wire wound around the dielectric to make it as a helix like structure. In [7] and [11], antipodal and notched antipodal Vivaldi antennas respectively are proposed for brain tumor detection. The antennas have small size, high directivity, low profile, wide bandwidth, and are easy to fabricate.

Figure 2.1: Classification Based on Biomedical Application

Printed antennas such as folded dipoles were proposed in [8] for microwave imaging and brain hyperthermia treatment. Two different designs were fabricated - one for a single band at 433 MHz and the other for a dual band at 433 MHz and 850 MHz. A water loaded metal diagonal horn antenna with good penetration depth was investigated in [9]. Another horn antenna developed in [11] was used for breast cancer hyperthermia treatment. The horn was dielectric loaded, Yagi-Uda fed, with improved gain directivity, reduced side lobe level, with good efficiency over dual frequency bands from 3 to 3.78 GHz and from 4.76 to 4.9 GHz.

b) Microwave Imaging

i) Breast Cancer Detection

Breast cancer is the most common invasive cancer in women, and it is the second main cause of death in women, after lung cancer. Early detection of such disease can significantly reduce the mortality rate. Noninvasive and harmless microwave breast imaging represents a promising alternative or a complimentary tool to mammography. In [12], Tissue Sensing Adaptive Radar (TSAR) for Microwave Breast Cancer detection was developed. As a basic design, the authors used the slotline bowtie hybrid antenna. Another design [13] of a MIS consisted of an array of tapered slot antennas immersed in a liquid with high dielectric constant to achieve good matching with the breast tissue. Microwave UWB radar for breast cancer localization was presented in [14], which consisted of a bowtie dipole antenna. In [15] an array of 16 element antenna was used in MIS for breast cancer detection. The array consisted of two type of antennas, namely Travelling Wave Tapered and Loaded Transmission Line antennas.

ii) Brain Stroke Detection

Worldwide, brain-stroke is the leading cause of adult disability. Stroke occurs when the blood supply in a part of

brain is disturbed when a blood vessel bursts or when blocked by a clot [18]. In this survey, we consider several antennas used for stroke detection. The group from the University of Queensland, Australia, proposed several imaging systems [16-19] for the same. In [16], a circular array consisting of compact (24 mm × 24 mm), corrugated microstrip-fed tapered slot antennas was proposed. The array was immersed in a suitable coupling liquid for improved matching with the brain tissues. Later, they proposed a system based on antipodal exponentially corrugated tapered-slot antenna [17]. The antennas were designed to operate across 1.1-4 GHz, which is widely used for head imaging. In [18] directional folded dipoles were used to achieve a high front to back ratio over the operation band of 1.23 to 2.75 GHz. Further, they developed a novel UWB antenna consisting of a folded dipole-like structure printed on two dielectric slabs of the same size [19]. This antenna covered bandwidth from 0.77 to 2.25 GHz with stable directional radiation patterns and an average gain of 4.5 dBi and front to back ratio of 8 dBi.

A group of researchers from Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Turkey investigated that shorted patch antenna model with planar inverted feed can be used to compensate inductance which is generated by increasing the height of the substrate to increase the bandwidth [20]. It contains an antenna with coaxial probe feed on a planar inverted type structure. The antenna has two parallel arms of same length but different widths. The proposed design was of dimension of 60 × 60 × 20.4 mm³. In context to localization of stroke, authors from Hanyang University, South Korea, has developed an antenna to generate EM pulse for better penetration depth [21]. The proposed antenna consists of an elliptical radiating patch, two slots and a high pass filters to generate the aforementioned pulse. The proposed antenna has 10 dB return loss bandwidths from 0.7 GHz to 2 GHz (high frequency band) and from 0.518 GHz to 0.525 GHz (low frequency band). In [22], a Microwave system is proposed as best possible solution for pre-hospital diagnosis. It claims of decreasing the time between injury and treatment. The paper brings forward a MIS consisting of measurement strategy, antenna types with array number and scattering signal measurement method.

iii) Brain Tumor Detection

In [23] an antenna is proposed for brain tumor detection, operating at Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) band (2.4-2.4835 GHz). The system used wearable pentagon shaped microstrip patch antennas, on FR-4 substrate.

c) Biotelemetry

In order to remotely monitor various vital signs, flexible and thin antennas are required to conform to patients' skin. One such kind is proposed in [24] with CPW fed and fabricated on Kapton Polyamide substrate due to its good balance of physical, chemical and electrical properties. In [25], the authors presented the design and simulation of a hexagonal shaped microstrip antenna along with a breast phantom. By introducing a co-centric hexagonal slot in the

center of a patch, to generate an outer hexagonal ring, an impedance bandwidth of 5 GHz is achieved.

i) Implantable Antennas

Implantable antennas are efficient implementations for biotelemetry and diagnosis of several diseases. Many research groups have proposed various antenna models for Implantable Medical Devices (IMDs). In 2009, a group of researchers developed a capsule shaped UWB antenna for medical implants, which covered bandwidth of 3.5-4.5 GHz [26]. Another research group investigated a compact dual band antenna operating in both MICS and ISM band [27]. The structure of antenna resembled a planar Inverted-F (PIFA) structure with two different substrate layers. In [28], a helical-folded dipole antenna for MICS band with central frequency of 924 MHz is reported.

ii) Wearable Antennas

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the body area networks (BAN). Particularly wireless biomedical telemetry between implantable devices and external equipment has been attracting considerable attention for diagnostic and monitoring purposes. In this view, several wearable antennas for on-body and off-body communication have been proposed [29-34]. In [29] a small PIFA is reported which consists of an etched U-shaped slot for dual band operation for wearable and ubiquitous computing equipment. In [30], the coupled planar dipole UWB antenna design were demonstrated for wearable computer applications. The design is developed from multi-band antenna concept and general coupling equivalent circuit concepts of narrowband antennas. In this progress, to achieve better flexibility and compactness a dual polarized printed antenna was proposed in [31] at 433.3 MHz. The antenna consisted of different substrates. The antenna achieved a high efficiency and wider bandwidth from 415 MHz to 445 MHz. In [32], author investigated a monopole antenna array of sixteen elements as a flexible geometry on Kapton Polyimide substrate for radar based cancer detection. Different antennas were embedded with clothes for biotelemetry, in [33], where a button shape antenna was made on a polyamide substrate with a coaxial feed for high data rate applications. Further, [34] presents a compact, dual-band, flexible, co-planar waveguide (CPW)-fed antenna at ISM band.

B. Classification of Antennas with Respect to the Operating Frequency Bands

Various frequency ranges investigated in biomedical applications. Commonly accepted frequency range covers 0.1 – 10 GHz for medical diagnosis. For example, in imaging applications, the optimal frequency band is about 1-3 GHz. In addition to this, we studied commonly known frequency bands dedicated to other medical applications. Firstly, we discuss about Medical Implant Communication Services (MICS) bands with frequency allocations 402-405 MHz and 433-434 MHz [35]. Later, we consider Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) bands, which are

902-908 MHz and 2.4-2.48 GHz [38], [40]. Ultra Wide Band (UWB) systems are suitable for low power consumption, low power output and high range resolution. The UWB range is 3.1-10.6 GHz [46] and it has proven as a potential candidate for wireless off body and on-body communication. In this section, as shown in Fig. 2.2, we discuss the chronological evolution of antenna designs operating at different frequency bands.

a) MICS Band

Proposed antennas in MICS bands are compact in size with good gain to reduce power consumption and save energy. In [35], a miniaturized slot PIFA antenna investigated for implantable communications. By changing the position of the slot, the antenna had a triple-band. Another PIFA antenna with multilayered configuration described in [36]. The antenna had two circular patches and a single ground plane. The patches were mirror images of each other. Later, a compact rectangular Planar Inverted-F patch antenna with shorting pin and slots [37], was fabricated on Rogers RO3210. The high permittivity of this substrate enables miniaturization.

Figure 2.2: Classification of Antennas based on Frequency Bands.

b) ISM Band

ISM bands systems use radio frequency for scientific and medical purposes. In 2010, dual band G-shape wearable cuff button antennas were proposed in [38] for small, low cost and efficient radiation performance. Later in [39], a Z-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed was developed and build on a biocompatible ceramic substrate with relative permittivity of 9.8. In the paper [40], a printed loop antenna with copper layer on both sides of substrate Rogers RT3010 with a thickness of 17 μm was proposed. The antenna had two shorting pins placed at the center for in-body communication. Several authors decided to use FR-4 substrate due to its availability. One of such kind, presented in [41], was a T-shaped patch. The ground plane was a combination of I-shape and spiral shape structure. In [42], the antenna design was accounted to achieve maximum SAR. In this study, the authors compared a stacked slotted triangular patch antenna and a stacked slotted square patch antenna. In the paper [43], a hexagonal patch antenna designed and fabricated on FR-4 substrate for ISM band medical applications. Later in [44], the authors fabricated a single-fed wideband implantable antenna with two shorting pins and a superstrate.

c) UWB Band

UWB range has wide variety of applications in military, civilian and commercial sectors. UWB has the capability to achieve high data rates over short distances, which makes it, the best candidate for biotelemetry and medical diagnostics. In this context, several antennas designs were proposed and fabricated. In the paper [45], the authors designed a double rigged horn antenna to work as a radar sensor for medical usage. Another geometry is a discone antenna as a modification of biconical antenna to enhance the directivity in the same frequency band, investigated in [46]. Patch antennas have always played a vital role in UWB range. For example, in [47], a fork-shaped slotted patch antenna developed for on-body and in-body communications. Researchers discovered different geometries to enhance the usability of antennas in the medical field one of such design is a fractal shaped antenna, named as Flamenco, fabricated and shown in [48] and which has five resonant frequencies.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper represents a chronological survey of various antenna models as a development of library of antennas for clinical purposes, which reliably provides a tool for microwave imaging and related applications. A detailed structural classification of biomedical applications like hyperthermia, biotelemetry and microwave imaging are investigated to study the applicability of antennas along with MICS, ISM and UWB frequency bands. In this paper, various antennas structures displayed as potential candidates for a future numerical library, which enables easy and efficient test conditions for their system design to various engineers working in microwave imaging field.

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